

THE TREATMENT OF DUENAL INJURIES

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Summary. *The paper presents the results of diagnostics and features of treatment of traumatic damage to the duodenum for 20 years. The analysis of the results of surgical treatment of 82 patients with closed injuries and wounds of the duodenum was carried out. In the early stages after trauma, the imposition of a duodenojejunosomy is, in our opinion, the best. Separation of duodenum from the digestive system (diverticulation) and operations on the drainage of the stomach, as well as duodenostomy were effective, when the disease was damaged more than half of the duodenum.*

Keywords. *Damage to the duodenum, surgical treatment*

Relevance researches. Ddiagnosis and treatment of duodenal injury (DPK), especially in the retroperitoneal part, is currently the most difficult and urgent problem of emergency abdominal surgery., the difficulty of the problem is related to the lack of a clear and characteristic clinical picture, and its rarity. To date, the incidence of duodenal injury in the structure of abdominal injuries is about 1.2% -2 and does not exceed 10% in the structure of digestive injuries. The greatest difficulties in making a timely diagnosis are noted with injuries to the retroperitoneal part of the duodenum, which are not diagnosed in 10-30% of victims.

Damage to the duodenum (DPK) is one of the most difficult situations for a surgeon, determined primarily by the problem of choosing surgical tactics for treating such patients. Until now, there is no unified surgical tactics in patients with this pathology. With severe injuries of the duodenum, various methods are used.* reconstructive interventions (switching off from of the digestive system, application of gastroetheroanastamosis, pancreatoduodenal resection) [14, 15]. Based on scientific works, the authors point out a large number of complications and high mortality in this category of patients. In the postoperative period, 35-55% of patients develop complications: failure of duodenal sutures, duodenal stump (during cut-off or resection operations), pancreatitis, retroperitoneal phlegmon. As a result, the mortality rate for duodenal injury is 11-30%, and with the development of retroperitoneal phlegmon, it can reach up to 100%.Analysis of the results of surgical treatment and justification of the optimal amount of surgical care for patients with duodenal injuries.

The work is based on the results of examination and treatment of more than 82 patients with various mechanical devices damage to the duodenum patients

who were examined and treated in Samarkand, Surkhandarya region, Kashkadarya Region, Jizzakh branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care for the period from 2000 to 2020

Was carried out nasogastroduodenal active aspiration, installation of an intestinal probe for nutrition, drainage of retroperitoneal tissue. In all cases, the operation was complemented by duodenostomy and cholecystostomy.

V degree of damage to the duodenum (detachment of the Vater papilla, common bile duct or the head of the pancreas from the wall of the duodenum, massive damage to the pancreatoduodenal zone due to crushing of the duodenum and the head of the pancreas) was diagnosed in 3 victims. In 1 case, pancreatoduodenal resection with unloading jejunostomy was performed. Two patients died during surgery due to profuse bleeding.

Discussion. At the present stage, the treatment of victims with duodenal lesions remains a difficult task that requires further study. The development of new diagnostic techniques and the choice of operations for extensive damage to the duodenum with adequate drug therapy will help reduce the number of postoperative complications and mortality in this severe category of patients.

Conclusions. Decompression through a tube with constant aspiration of duodenal contents in the postoperative period is an effective measure for the prevention of suture failure and traumatic pancreatitis. In the early stages after trauma, the imposition of a duodenojejunostomy is, in our opinion, the best. In the later periods after the injury, the imposition of duodenostomy along with the disconnection of the duodenum and with drainage operations on the stomach gave good results.

Literature

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